

Studies on the Interaction of Binary Clay Mixtures in Aqueous and Acetone Media by Means of Electrometric Measurements

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Water molecules being highly polar are maximally bonded to clay particles and are hence likely to influence clay-clay interaction. The role of water molecules in interaction of binary clay mixtures was studied by means of electrochemical measurements altering the medium to one of low dielectric constant. The variation of c.e.c. values indicates a lower percentage of interaction in aqueous acetone medium.

THE electrochemical behaviour of binary mixture of different clays in aqueous medium¹⁻⁴ revealed the mutual influence of one upon the other, and there was a decrease in c.e.c. values from that of the summation of c.e.c. values of two single clays present in the mixture. Water being a highly polar solvent is maximally bonded to clay particles and influences the clay-clay interaction. But if water is partially replaced by a less polar liquid, the hydration of clay particles will alter affecting the so called interaction.

Although kaolinite showed⁵ dibasic character in aqueous medium and smectite should exhibit three inflections, only one inflection of smectite in the potentiometric titration of K-bentonite in glycol with HCl was reported⁶. The possibility of "immobilisation" of clay particles in non-aqueous medium e.g. clay suspension in ethanol was suggested⁷ and led to the lowering of exchangeability of cations. This decrease of exchangeability was caused by decrease in dielectric constant of the medium. In the present study it was of interest to find out how the medium affects clay-clay interaction as it is changed from water to a less polar component. To ascertain the extent of interaction electrometric measurements were carried out both in aqueous medium and acetone-water medium (50 : 50) which has a much lower dielectric constant than water.

X-ray diffraction shows that the smectite was more or less pure but the kaolinite sample contained small percentages of mica and smectite as impurities. The latter did not substantially influence the electrometric measurements.

Experimental

Two clays, smectite and kaolinite, are chosen as they are widely different in properties. The fraction below two microns was isolated from each of the

samples according to the usual procedure⁸. Fine subfractions were obtained by allowing the dispersion to settle for 72 hr at room temperature and siphoning off the material in suspension. The organic matter was separated from the clay by treatment with hydrogen peroxide. Free oxides of iron, aluminium and silicon were removed by dithionite-citrate-bicarbonate method and finally washed with alcohol, dialysed and freed from chloride ion. The clays were stored as aqueous colloidal suspension.

Preparation of H-clay: Each sample of clay was converted to H-clay by equilibrating with H-resin (Amberlite IR 120) suspension in cellophane bags and replacing the H-resin twice or thrice with fresh samples until the pH of the clay suspensions was constant. H-clays thus prepared were stored in Jena glass bottles and their colloid contents determined.

H-smectite and H-kaolinite were mixed at different proportions and kept for 7 days with occasional stirring. This method holds for the aqueous and the acetone media.

Cation exchange capacity determination: The c.e.c. values of H-clays were determined by using KCl-KOH method⁹.

Electrochemical measurements: Potentiometric and conductometric titrations of H-smectite and H-kaolinite against 0.01 N NaOH were carried out by continuous method at different concentration of clays in aqueous medium and acetone-water (50 : 50) medium. Elico pH meter and Elico conductivity bridge were used. The same titrations were done in case of clays in the two media.

Results and Discussion

It was observed from the titration curves (some typical of which are shown in Figs. 1 and 2) that in

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aqueous acetone medium H-kaolinite shows nearly similar weak acidity features as in the pure aqueous system, but a somewhat higher c.e.c. values than that in the aqueous medium. With dilution of the clay suspensions, the pH values increase but the c.e.c. values slightly decrease. From the curves it is seen that the c.e.c. values of the suspensions having the same concentration were higher in aqueous acetone than in pure aqueous medium. The same kind of acidic characteristics of H-smectite was observed both in aqueous and aqueous acetone medium with lowering of c.e.c. with decreasing colloid content. But c.e.c. values were markedly higher than those in aqueous medium. The double inflection in the titration curves of H-smectite in aqueous acetone medium was a little more pronounced in the case of suspensions having lower colloid content. From the data given in Table 1 it was observed that the c.e.c. values of the mixtures were lower than the additive values, as happens for clay minerals in aqueous medium. From the difference, the percentage interaction of the two clay, in both medium, was calculated.

Fig. 1. pH-titration curves of H-smectite and H-kaolinite in aqueous and aqueous acetone medium.

Fig. 2. pH-titration curves of the mixture of H-kaolinite and H-smectite in aqueous and acetone medium.

The neutralisation of an H-clay (H-smectite or H-kaolinite) with caustic soda may take place in two steps, namely,

The first is an exchange reaction which is determined by the degree of solvation of the Na^+ ion. Larger solution of Na^+ leading to an increase in its size would hinder the exchange reaction. In water alone Na^+ ion would hydrate perhaps more than in a mixture of water and acetone. If that is so, the exchange would be facilitated in aqueous acetone and hence a higher c.e.c. may be expected. On the other hand, higher solvation (hydration in water alone) would mean greater availability of surface. In case of aqueous acetone, a greater degree of aggregation is likely and hence loss of availability of surface. Consequently, exchange will be hindered. Thus, in aqueous acetone medium the resultant of these two opposing factors would determine the c.e.c. Apparently, acetone in aqueous acetone medium hinders the hydration of Na^+ ion and hence facilitates exchange for H^+ of H-clays. Hydration increases the size of Na^+ ion causing decrease in exchange. On the other hand, decrease in hydration of Na^+ ion in aqueous acetone medium causes an increase in c.e.c. values.

The features of titration curves of binary mixtures of H-smectite and H-kaolinite aqueous and aqueous acetone medium are similar in both. The c.e.c. values increase as expected with increasing proportions of H-smectite in the mixture. But the percentage lowering of c.e.c. decreases with increasing concentration of H-smectite in aqueous system.

Fig. 3. Interaction of clay mixture in different solvent.

This percentage of lowering of c.e.c. may be taken to be a measure of percentage of interaction (Table 1). The minimum interaction occurs at c.e.c. ratio of 6.25 and weight ratio of 1 and a small maximum occurs at c.e.c. ratio=1, weight ratio=5.0. The decrease in c.e.c. values of binary mixture from the additive c.e.c. values of individual clays in aqueous acetone medium is much less (Fig. 3), which suggests that the degree of interaction is much smaller in aqueous acetone than in water

TABLE 1—PERCENTAGE OF INTERACTION OF CLAY MIXTURE IN AQUEOUS AND IN AQUEOUS ACETONE MEDIUM

Individual c.c. in g percent in aqueous medium		Individual c.c. in g percent in aqueous acetone medium		c.c.c. ratio in aqueous medium	c.c.c. ratio in aqueous acetone medium	Percentage of interaction	
Smectite	Kaolinite	Smectite	Kaolinite			water	acetone
0.012	0.11	—	—	4.6 : 8 = 0.5	—	32.8	—
0.0354	0.0857	0.036	0.081	14 : 5.9 = 2.3	24 : 6.6 = 3.6	35.0	18.0
0.059	0.061	0.0585	0.059	25 : 4 = 6.25	42 : 4.5 = 9.3	14.0	4.5
0.082	0.0867	0.081	0.0356	37 : 2.26 = 16.3	68 : 25 = 25.2	21.3	4.6
0.106	0.0122	—	—	49.5 : 71 = 70.7	—	17.1	—

(Table 1). However, here also the maximum interaction is observed at about 1 : 1 c.c.c. ratio (Fig. 3).

References

1. S. K. CHAKRABARTI and S. K. MUKHERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 169.
2. B. CHATTERJEE and M. SARKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 261.
3. B. CHATTERJEE and M. SARKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **28**, 717.
4. M. SARKAR and B. CHATTERJEE, *Bull. Natl. Inst. Sc. India*, 1964, **26**, 184.
5. R. P. MITRA, *Bull. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1942, **4**, 41.
6. A. K. GANGULI, L. M. MUKHERJEE and S. B. GHOSH, *Science and Culture*, 1959, **19**, 42.
7. A. CHATTERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 395.
8. G. W. ROBINSON and M. RICHARDSON, *Imp. Bur. Soil Sci. Tech. Bull.*, 1933, **26**, 1.
9. A. K. GANGULI and S. K. MUKHERJEE, *J. Phys. Colloid Chem.*, 1951, **55**, 1429.